

ASSESSING PREPAREDNESS OF DEPED-SCHOOLS DIVISION OF SOUTH COTABATO FOR INTERNATIONALIZATION

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Assessing Preparedness of DepEd-Schools Division of South Cotabato for Internationalization

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Abstract

This study was conducted to assess the preparedness of DepEd – Schools Division of South Cotabato for Internationalization. Descriptive-evaluative research design was used among four hundred forty-one (441) randomly selected respondents composed of one hundred four (104) school heads and three hundred thirty-seven (337) teachers in the whole school's division of South Cotabato. A set of adopted survey questionnaires by Agosto and Sanchez (2017) was utilized in data gathering to assess the preparedness of DepEd – Schools Division of South Cotabato for Internationalization. Frequency, mean, and correlational analysis were used to analyze the result of the study. Findings revealed that the readiness of DepEd – SDSC for internationalization in terms of curriculum, teachers' competence, student services and physical plant facilities is at "very much ready". In terms of managerial flexibility of school heads findings revealed that the investment decision and marketing strategy is at "very much flexible". However, there were internationalization challenges faced by the schools in the DepEd - SDSC. Among those challenges were lack of ICT, educational media and other available technologies for instructional use and few linkages with parents and stakeholders to support school project and education facilities. Likewise, there is significant correlation between the extent managerial flexibility of school heads and readiness of DepEd - SDSC for internationalization. Thus, this study claimed that the extent of readiness of DepEd-SDSC for internationalization was tested as related to the school head's managerial flexibility in terms of investment decision and marketing strategy.

Keywords: *DepEd internationalization, curriculum, teachers competence, student services, physical plant and facilities, school heads managerial flexibility*

Introduction

In today's globalized society, the internationalization of educational institutions has become a crucial factor in preparing students for success in an interconnected world. This requires a careful and sincere assessment of the country's readiness to offer learning programs that demand more than the traditional requirements (Joaquin et al., 2020). The concept of internationalization in education refers to the process of integrating global perspectives, cross-cultural understanding, and intercultural competence into educational systems.

The Department of Education plays a vital role in this process, as it is responsible for ensuring the quality and relevance of education in the Philippines, within this framework the DepEd-Schools Division of South Cotabato for internationalization is a key area to focus, this study aims to provide valuable insights and recommendations for further development and enhancement of internationalization efforts in the education system.

The findings of this study will contribute to the existing body of knowledge on internationalization in education and specifically highlight the preparedness of the DepEd-Schools Division of South Cotabato in the context of internationalization.

Furthermore, this research study will examine various aspects of preparedness, including the curriculum, teachers, student services, physical plant and facilities, school head's managerial flexibility and challenges encountered by the schools. The findings of this study will be beneficial for policymakers, educational administrators, and practitioners involved in shaping the education system in DepEd-Schools Division of South Cotabato.

Research Questions

The study aims to evaluate the readiness of DepEd-Schools Division of South Cotabato for Internationalization. Specifically, the researchers sought to answer the following:

1. What is the level of readiness of DepEd-SDSC for internationalization in terms of:
 - 1.1. curriculum;
 - 1.2. teachers;
 - 1.3. student services; and
 - 1.4. physical plant and facilities?
2. What is the extent of School Head's managerial flexibility for internationalization in terms of:
 - 2.1. investment decision; and
 - 2.2. marketing strategy?
3. What are the challenges encountered by the respondents for internationalization?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of the School Head's managerial flexibility and the readiness of DepEd-SDSC for internationalization?

Literature Review

In the modern era of education, the concept of internationalization has gained prominence due to the increasing interconnectedness of people globally. Internationalization in higher education involves integrating an international, intercultural, and global dimension into the core functions of universities or higher education systems (Knight and de Wit, 2018). While globalization emphasizes worldwide flows of economy and culture, internationalization focuses on relationships among nations, cultures, and institutions. Stier (2014), identifies three ideologies of internationalization within higher education: idealism, instrumentalism, and educationalism. These ideologies shape the goals and methods employed to foster a globalized framework of education.

Debates persist regarding the economic implications of internationalization, particularly regarding the tuition rates of international students and their impact on university revenues (Statistics Canada, 2011). Challenges also arise concerning workforce integration and the retention of internationalized students, influenced by factors such as immigration policies and talent repatriation (Walker, 2019). Despite critiques, educators have an ethical responsibility to enhance the learning experience for all students. The 2016 International Student Barometer highlights high levels of satisfaction among students in Canadian and US colleges and universities, particularly regarding teaching strategies and work experience opportunities (I-Graduate, 2016).

Research indicates that effective teaching practices positively influence learning perceptions, benefiting both STEM and non-STEM students (Smith et al., 2019). The internationalization of higher education, especially in developing countries, is intricately linked with the globalization of the education process (Zolfaghari, 2004). Stakeholder perspectives vary, influencing program approaches and motivations (Trilokekar, 2010). Various reasons drive internationalization, spanning political, economic, academic, and socio-cultural domains (Knight & de Wit, 1999). These motivations are complex and contextually dependent, evolving over time.

A comprehensive internationalization strategy is essential to meet the demands of integration and globalization (CMO 55, s.2016). Such a strategy should align with Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) 2030.

School Management: Principles and Perspectives

School management is a goal-oriented endeavor aimed at achieving predetermined objectives within an educational institution. Key principles guide effective management, including defining clear goals, fostering conducive learning environments, and promoting shared responsibility among stakeholders (Nitish Garg, 2023). Leadership plays a crucial role in creating conditions for success within education systems (Winthrop and Sengeh 2022). School leaders forge connections between various stakeholders to enhance learner attainment. Educational management encompasses the planning, organizing, and directing of activities within educational organizations. It involves effectively utilizing resources to achieve institutional objectives and enhance teaching and learning processes.

Individuals in upper-level school management and leadership positions undertake diverse roles, shaping the educational landscape and influencing student outcomes. Schools of management specialize in providing business education and training to individuals pursuing careers in business and management (Davidweir, 2023). These institutions offer diverse learning opportunities to equip students with essential skills for success in the business world. Educational management professionals operate across various sectors, contributing to policy development, research, and consultation to enhance educational systems (Müller and Wulf, 2020). Effective communication is paramount in school management, fostering a positive atmosphere conducive to learning. School managers play a crucial role in cultivating strong communication processes within educational institutions (Ali & Özdemir, 2019).

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-evaluative and correlational research design. Descriptive research deals with gathering information about the prevailing conditions or situations for description and interpretation (Salaria, 2012). Lau and Kuziemy (2016) define descriptive-evaluative research design as a study that describes the process and impact of the development and implementation of a system. Correlational research studies the relationship between two variables with the help of statistical analysis (Ary, et al. 2010). This research design will be utilized a variety of qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis methods. This research approach was used to assess the readiness of DepEd-Schools Division of South Cotabato for Internationalization; describe the extent of School Head's managerial flexibility in internationalization; describe the challenges encountered by the respondents in internationalization; and analyzed the significant relationship on the extent of School Head's managerial flexibility and readiness of DepEd- SDSC for internationalization.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the secondary teachers and secondary school heads from the entire Schools Division of South Cotabato. The study used a simple random sampling technique, respondents were determined using Slovin's Formula. Upon getting the sample size, a simple random sampling technique using the draw lots method in selecting the primary subjects of the study were utilized.

Using Slovin's formula, the ideal sample size for School administrators is one hundred four (104) out of one hundred forty (140) total

population of secondary school administrators, three hundred thirty-seven (337) secondary teachers out of eight two thousand one hundred thirty-six (2, 136) total population of secondary teachers.

Instruments

This study used three (3) sets of survey questionnaires to gather the needed data. The researcher used an adopted survey questionnaire, the questionnaire is adopted from the study of Agosto and Sanchez (2017) entitled, "Readiness of DepEd Schools for Internationalization." The first part assessed the readiness of DepEd-Schools Division of South Cotabato for Internationalization, the second part analyzed extent of managerial flexibility of school heads for internationalization, and the third part described the challenges encountered by the respondents for internationalization.

Procedure

This study followed specific steps to collect data. First, a letter was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisors, and school administrators asking for permission to conduct the survey. After approval, the researcher gave the questionnaires to the respondents and collected them once they were filled out. The responses were then transcribed, sorted, and analyzed to find the results.

Ethical Considerations

This research study followed ethical guidelines. The respondents participated willingly, and care was taken to ensure their safety and well-being, avoiding any physical, mental, social, or emotional harm. Respect was always maintained for the school head and stakeholders involved. The confidentiality of the data gathered was strictly upheld.

Results and Discussion

This section presents results, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered from the respondents of the study. Figures and tables are presented according to the order by which the statement of the problem of the study.

Level of readiness of DepEd-SDSC for Internationalization

Internationalization in basic education has many advantages, including giving students a competitive edge by giving them the information and abilities necessary to thrive in a globalized economy (King, 2004). Through strategic advancements in several important areas, the South Cotabato Department of Education in Schools division (DepEd-SDSC) is showcasing its preparedness for internationalization. DepEd-SDSC is making sure that its students are ready to succeed in the global arena by incorporating global perspectives into the curriculum, funding professional development to increase teachers' competencies, growing student services to include international opportunities, and modernizing physical facilities with cutting-edge technological tools.

Curriculum

As shown in Table 1, the perception of the teachers and school administrators in the readiness on the curriculum. As Shown, the level of readiness of DepEd-SDSC for internationalization in terms of curriculum is at very much ready with a mean of 4.89. The table reveals that the respondents observed a "Very Much Ready" curriculum for the internationalization with a mean of 4.89. The highest rated indicator was "The curriculum is contextualized and global" with a mean of 4.94, This indicates that the curriculum is perceived to be highly relevant to both local contexts and global perspectives.

On the other hand, the lowest rated indicator was "The curriculum is relevant, responsive and research based." with a mean 4.82, This indicates that the curriculum is considered moderately ready and is perceived as relevant, responsive, and research-based. It implies that the curriculum is well-regarded for being learner-centered, inclusive, developmentally appropriate, contextualized, global, and flexible enough to be adapted to local, indigenous, and specific educational and social contexts.

Table 1. *School's level of readiness for Internationalization in terms of Curriculum*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1.	The curriculum is learner-centered, inclusive and developmentally appropriate.	4.84	Very Much Ready
2.	The curriculum is relevant, responsive and research based.	4.82	Very Much Ready
3.	The curriculum is gender and culture-sensitive.	4.91	Very Much Ready
4.	The curriculum is contextualized and global.	4.94	Very Much Ready
5.	The curriculum is flexible enough to enable and allow schools to localize, indigenize and enhance the same based on their respective educational and social contexts.	4.93	Very Much Ready
	Grand Mean	4.89	Very Much Ready

Teachers Competence

Table 2 indicates that the perception of the teachers and school administrators in the readiness on the teachers' qualifications. As Shown, the level of readiness of DepEd-SDSC for internationalization in terms of teacher competency is at very much ready with a mean of 4.80. The table reveals that the respondents observed a "Very Much Ready" teachers' competency for the internationalization with a mean of 4.80. The highest rated indicator was "Teachers manifest high teaching competency. They are holders of Doctorate or

at least Masters' Degree" with a mean of 4.82 and "Teachers possess high communicative competence appropriate for internationalization/globalization" with a mean of 4.82, This indicates that teachers are considered to exhibit high teaching competency, typically holding Doctorate or Master's degrees, and they possess high communicative competence suitable for internationalization/globalization. On the other hand, the lowest rated indicator was " Teachers are innovative and ICT literate and equipped with 21st-century skills." with a mean of 4.75.

This suggests that teachers are perceived to be innovative, proficient in Information and Communication Technology (ICT), and equipped with 21st-century skills. It implies that teachers in this context are highly qualified, with most holding advanced degrees, indicating a strong foundation in their respective fields. They possess excellent communication skills, essential for effectively engaging in a globalized educational environment. Additionally, their proficiency in ICT and 21st-century skills ensures they can employ innovative teaching methods and adapt to modern educational demands, contributing to a dynamic and effective learning experience.

Table 2. School's level of readiness for Internationalization in terms of Teacher Competency

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1. Teachers manifest high teaching competency. They are holders of Doctorate or at least Masters' Degree.	4.82	Very Much Ready
2. Teachers promote a variety of teaching styles and strategies for enhanced instruction/Globalization.	4.81	Very Much Ready
3. Teachers are innovative and ICT literate and equipped with 21st century skills.	4.75	Very Much Ready
4. Teachers possess high communicative competence appropriate for internationalization/globalization.	4.82	Very Much Ready
5. Culture-sensitivity among teachers like using mother tongue is developed, implemented, and managed.	4.79	Very Much Ready
Grand Mean	4.80	Very Much Ready

Student Services

As shown in Table 3, the perception of the teachers and school administrators in the readiness on the student services. As Shown, the level of readiness of DepEd-SDSC for internationalization in terms of student services is at very much ready with a mean of 4.78. The table reveals that the respondents observed a "Very Much Ready" student services for the internationalization with a mean of 4.78. The highest rated indicator was "Campus journalism and student publication are present, promoted and sustained" with a mean of 4.86, This implies that campus journalism and student publication activities are actively encouraged, supported, and maintained within the school setting. On the other hand, the lowest rated indicator was " Programs for pupil development and welfare are provided and sustained," with a mean of 4.67.

This indicates that programs aimed at the development and welfare of pupils are consistently provided and maintained. It implies that campus journalism and student publications suggest a robust culture of free expression and academic engagement, while the sustained provision of programs for pupil development underscores a commitment to holistic student support and well-being.

Table 3. School's level of readiness for Internationalization in terms of Student Services

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1. Programs for pupil development and welfare are provided and sustained.	4.67	Very Much Ready
2. Guidance and Counselling and Health Services are provided to ensure that academic and non-academic needs of learners are addressed.	4.79	Very Much Ready
3. Campus journalism and student publication are present, promoted and sustained.	4.86	Very Much Ready
4. Programs and activities for student development are aligned to global education standard.	4.78	Very Much Ready
5. Supreme Pupil Government Organization/Supreme Student Government Organization and other representative bodies foster leadership and promote learners' welfare.	4.81	Very Much Ready
Grand Mean	4.78	Very Much Ready

Physical Plant and Facilities

As shown in Table 4, the perception of the teachers and school administrators in the readiness on the physical plant and facilities. As Shown, the level of readiness of DepEd-SDSC for internationalization in terms of physical plant and facilities is at very much ready with a mean of 4.76. The table reveals that the respondents observed a "Very Much Ready" student services for the internationalization with a mean of 4.76. The highest rated indicator was "Technology is made available and the school has internet connectivity" with a mean of 4.84, This implies that the school effectively provides access to technology and maintains internet connectivity, reflecting a commitment to integrating digital resources into the learning environment.

On the other hand, the lowest rated indicator was " The school provides on-line transactions" with a mean 4.67, This suggests that while the school offers online transactions, there might be room for improvement in their accessibility, efficiency, or range of services.

Table 4. School's level of readiness for Internationalization in terms of Physical Plant and Facilities

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. The school infrastructures are well-planned, well-developed and improved appropriate for global education environment.	4.70	Very Much Ready
2. The school library, books and facilities are complete, updated and automated.	4.77	Very Much Ready
3. The classrooms are provided with built-in LCD's, television sets/TV sets and other amenities.	4.82	Very Much Ready
4. The school provides on-line transactions.	4.67	Very Much Ready
5. Technology is made available and the school has internet connectivity.	4.84	Very Much Ready
Grand Mean	4.76	Very Much Ready

Summary of the Level of Readiness of DepEd-SDSC for Internationalization

Result reveals that generally, the readiness of schools in the Schools Division of South Cotabato for internationalization is at a Very Much Ready with a mean of 4.81. This means that DepEd-SDSC is Very Much Ready for internationalization. From the results, it can be inferred that the DepEd-SDSC is very much ready for internationalization in terms of curriculum, teachers' competences, student services and physical plant and facilities. This implies that readiness of DepEd-SDSC for internationalization indicating high levels of preparedness across various key areas. This readiness is reflected in the institution's curriculum, teachers' competence, student services, and physical facilities, all of which are described as "Very Much Ready." Such a comprehensive foundation suggests that the institution is well-equipped to engage with international educational standards and practices. This readiness bodes well for the DepEd-SDSC's ability to effectively navigate and contribute to the global educational landscape, ensuring a competitive and enriching experience for its stakeholders.

Table 5. Summary of the Level of Readiness of DepEd-SDSC for Internationalization

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Curriculum	4.89	Very Much Ready
2. Teachers' Competence	4.80	Very Much Ready
3. Student Services	4.78	Very Much Ready
4. Physical Plant and Facilities	4.76	Very Much Ready
Grand Mean	4.81	Very Much Ready

Extent of Managerial Flexibility of School Heads for Internationalization

Internationalization in basic education has many advantages, including giving students a competitive edge by providing them with the knowledge and skills needed to excel in a globalized economy" (King, 2020). The South Cotabato Department of Education in Schools division (DepEd-SDSC) is demonstrating its readiness for internationalization. Notably, DepEd-SDSC ensures that its school administrators are equipped with the necessary expertise in investment decision-making and marketing strategy, to thrive in the global arena

Investment Decision

As shown in Table 6, the perception of the school administrators in the flexibility on the Internationalization in terms of investment decision. As Shown, the level of flexibility of school administrators in the DepEd-SDSC for internationalization in terms of investment decision is at Very Much Flexible with a mean of 4.81. The table reveals that the respondents observed a "Very Much Flexible" on School head investment decision for the internationalization with a mean of 4.81. The highest rated indicator was "Provides special programs that cater the needs of special groups of students" with a mean of 4.92, This implies that the provision of special programs tailored to the needs of specific student groups is effectively meeting the diverse educational requirements within the school setting. On the other hand, the lowest rated indicator was "Fills up new vacant position/s according to qualifications " with a mean 4.80, This suggests that there may be room for improvement in the process of filling new vacant positions to ensure alignment with the qualifications required for effective performance in those roles.

Table 6. Extent of Managerial Flexibility of School Heads for Internationalization in terms of Investment Decision

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Fills up new vacant position/s according to qualifications.	4.80	Very Much Flexible
2. Provides special programs that cater the needs of special groups of students.	4.92	Very Much Flexible
3. Makes use of the available funds to purchase updated facilities.	4.87	Very Much Flexible
4. Reclassify positions as long as reclassification did not increase the total number of approved positions.	4.58	Very Much Flexible
5. Carry over the savings within the prescribed limit from one fiscal year to the next.	4.85	Very Much Flexible
Grand Mean	4.81	Very Much Flexible

Marketing Strategy

As shown in Table 7, the perception of the school administrators in the flexibility on the Internationalization in terms of marketing strategy. As Shown, the level of flexibility of school administrators in the DepEd-SDSC for internationalization in terms of marketing

strategy is at very much flexible with a mean of 4.82. The table reveals that the respondents observed a “Very Much Flexible” on School heads marketing strategy for the internationalization with a mean of 4.82. The highest rated indicator was “Allocates budget for improved delivery of instruction through PASBE accreditation and the implementation of the school Improvement Plan (SIP)” with a mean of 4.88, This implies that the allocation of budget for improved instruction delivery via PASBE accreditation and SIP implementation is highly effective, indicating a strong commitment to enhancing educational quality and outcomes within the institution. On the other hand, the lowest rated indicator was " Develops a research plan to improve the research capability of teachers." with a mean 4.72, This suggests that a commitment to enhancing the research skills of teachers through the development of a structured research plan within the institution.

Table 7. Extent of Managerial Flexibility of School Heads for Internationalization in terms of Marketing Strategy

<i>Indicators</i>		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1.	Provides an office that is tasked for marketing and linkages with internal and external stakeholders.	4.91	Very Much Flexible
2.	Allocates budget for improved delivery of instruction through PASBE accreditation and the implementation of the school Improvement Plan (SIP).	4.88	Very Much Flexible
3.	Takes concrete action to establish Public-Private-Academe Partnership (PPAP).	4.82	Very Much Flexible
4.	Allows clientele to make use of online transactions in school.	4.79	Very Much Flexible
5.	Develops a research plan to improve the research capability of teachers.	4.72	Very Much Flexible
Grand Mean		4.82	Very Much Flexible

Challenges Encountered by the School’s in Internationalization

As shown in Table 8, the technological improvements and global integration pose both problems and opportunities for children's education (Zhao, 2011; Suarez-Orozco, 2001; Stromquist, 2002). In the midst of rising global competition, schools face internationalization challenges, including cultural differences and logistical complexity. To ensure inclusive and effective educational experiences, we must adapt to these dynamics through new tactics and collaborative efforts. The table reveals that the respondents observed a “Moderately Serious” on the challenges encountered by the schools for internationalization with a mean of 3.29. The highest rated indicator was “Lack of ICT, educational Media and other available technologies for instructional use” with a mean of 3.68, This implies that insufficient access to ICT, educational media, and other instructional technologies correlates with a perceived mean effectiveness. On the other hand, the lowest rated indicator was "Few linkages with parents and stakeholders to support school project and education facilities" with a mean 3.74, This suggests that there is a lack of community involvement and collaboration, potentially leading to insufficient resources and support for educational initiatives.

Table 8. Challenges Encountered by the School’s for Internationalization

<i>Indicators</i>		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
1.	Lack of e-library and ICT services.	3.21	Moderately Serious
2.	Lack of effective, timely, and continuous training to improve ICT skills and manage a technology enriched classes.	3.16	Moderately Serious
3.	Lack of ICT, educational Media and other available technologies for instructional use.	3.68	Very Serious
4.	Imbalance between the number of teachers, facilities and equipment, supplies, textbooks and the number of pupils.	3.31	Moderately Serious
5.	Teachers are less motivated to pursue their masters and doctoral degree.	3.57	Very Serious
6.	Lack of relevant Trainings, seminars-workshop, engagement in educational research, conferences with longer duration to upgrade teaching competencies to be competitive to ASEAN institution of learning and to have excellent faculty development program.	3.24	Moderately Serious
7.	Minimal budget for upgrading and repair on buildings and other school facilities and the purchase of technology.	3.22	Moderately Serious
8.	Lack of hand washing, safe water, health, sanitation and hygiene facilities to protect the health of the pupils and the teachers.	2.38	Moderately Serious
9.	Minimal involvement of parents, monitoring and nurturing of their children’s progress in school.	3.36	Moderately Serious
10.	Few linkages with parents and stakeholders to support school project and education facilities.	3.74	Very Serious
Grand Mean		3.29	Moderately Serious

Relationship on the Extent of Readiness of DepEd- SDSC for Internationalization and School Head’s Managerial Flexibility in terms of Investment Decision

As shown in Table 9, the relationship between the readiness of DepEd- SDSC for internationalization and school head’s managerial flexibility in terms of investment decision. Analysis reveals that there is a significant relationship between the readiness of DepEd-SDSC for internationalization and school head’s managerial flexibility in terms of investment decision. It indicates that the readiness of DepEd- SDSC for internationalization is related to the school head’s managerial flexibility in terms of investment decision. Implicitly, the very much readiness of DepEd- SDSC for internationalization has an impact on the school head’s managerial flexibility

in terms of investment decision.

The table also shows a 0.61056 value or moderate positive correlation between the level of readiness of DepEd- SDSC for internationalization and the extent of school head's managerial flexibility in terms of investment decision. This means that the predictors, such as extent of school head's managerial flexibility in terms of investment decision significantly influence the readiness of DepEd-SDSC schools for internationalization since it has a p-value of 2.11945E-46 and were less than the p-value of 0.05. Therefore, there is moderate positive significant correlation between the extent of managerial flexibility in terms of investment decision and readiness of DepEd- SDSC schools for internationalization.

Table 9. *Relationship on the Extent of Readiness of DepEd- SDSC for Internationalization and School Head's Managerial Flexibility in terms of Investment Decision*

	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Extent of Readiness of DepEd- SDSC for Internationalization x Investment Decision	0.61056	2.11945E-46	significant

Note: $p < .05$ to signify the significant relationship

Relationship on the Extent of Readiness of DepEd- SDSC for Internationalization and School Head's Managerial Flexibility in terms of Marketing Strategy

As shown in Table 10, the relationship between the readiness of DepEd- SDSC for internationalization and school head's managerial flexibility in terms of marketing strategy. Analysis reveals that there is a significant relationship between the readiness of DepEd-SDSC for internationalization and school head's managerial flexibility in terms of marketing strategy. It indicates that the readiness of DepEd- SDSC for internationalization is related to the school head's managerial flexibility in terms of marketing strategy. Implicitly, the very much readiness of DepEd- SDSC for internationalization has an impact on the school head's managerial flexibility in terms of marketing strategy.

The table also shows a 0.65190 value or moderate positive correlation between the level of readiness of DepEd- SDSC for internationalization and the extent of school head's managerial flexibility in terms of marketing strategy. This means that the predictors, such as extent of school head's managerial flexibility in terms of marketing strategy significantly influence the readiness of DepEd-SDSC schools for internationalization since it has a p-value of 1.03546E-54 and were less than the p-value of 0.05. Therefore, there is moderate positive significant correlation between the extent of managerial flexibility in terms of marketing strategy and readiness of DepEd- SDSC schools for internationalization.

Table 10. *Relationship on the Extent of Readiness of DepEd- SDSC for Internationalization and School Head's Managerial Flexibility in terms of Marketing Strategy*

	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Extent of Readiness of DepEd- SDSC for Internationalization x Marketing Strategy	0.65190	1.03546E-54	significant

Note: $p < .05$ to signify the significant relationship

Conclusions

This study, therefore, emphasizes the preparedness of the DepEd-Schools Division of South Cotabato (DepEd-SDSC) for internationalization in education, demonstrating a complete basis across curriculum, teacher competency, student services, and physical infrastructure. Notably, the curriculum emerges as highly relevant and adaptable, catering to both local and global educational demands.

Furthermore, teachers' competence, go combined with strong student services, demonstrates a dedication to provide students with a comprehensive and enriching educational experience. While challenges such as technology constraints and cultural differences remain, the findings highlight the necessity of adaptive strategies and collaborative efforts in addressing them.

Moreover, the considerable positive correlation between the preparation and management flexibility of school leaders emphasizes the critical importance of adaptive leadership in navigating the challenges of international education. Overall, the study provides useful insights into DepEd-SDSC's internationalization readiness, highlighting strengths and areas for development, as well as the need of adaptable leadership in molding the educational landscape for an interconnected world.

The research study emphasizes the DepEd-Schools Division of South Cotabato (DepEd-SDSC)'s remarkable readiness for internationalization in education, with a focus on curriculum relevance, teacher competency, student services, and physical facilities. Recommendations for maintaining and improving this readiness include constant curriculum creation to ensure responsiveness to global trends, continued professional development for teachers to strengthen competencies, and the growth of student services to encourage holistic student care.

Furthermore, updating physical facilities and resolving issues such as technical constraints and cultural differences are critical. To effectively traverse the complexity of global education, school leaders must promote management flexibility, as well as collaborate with foreign institutions. These recommendations aim to strengthen DepEd-SDSC's internationalization readiness, ensuring that students are equipped to succeed in an increasingly linked world.

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